

Data Management Plan II

Action Acronym: PEACE

Action title: Project 101101343 - Pressurized Efficient Alkaline Electrolyser

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PEACE project members

Beneficiary name	Short name
Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DE)	DLR
Materials Mates Italia SRL (IT)	MMI
Technische Universiteit Eindhoven (NL)	TU/e
Brandenburgische Technische Universität Cottbus Senftenberg (DE)	BTU
Grant Garant sro (CZ)	GG
HyCC B.V. (NL)	HYCC
Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DK)	DTU

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AEL	Alkaline electrolysis
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence
CC-BY-SA	Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike Licence
CC0	Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication
DMP	Data Management Plan
EB	Executive Board
FMEA	Failure Mode and Effects Analysis
HAZOP	Hazard and Operability Analysis
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
M	Month
PEDR	Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results
PM	Person-month
WP	Work package

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1. Executive Summary

This document represents an update of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the PEACE project - a research and innovation action project financed by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership (CHP) under the Horizon Europe programme. The PEACE project is coordinated by Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DLR). The main objective of the project is to reduce the levelized cost of hydrogen via the development of an innovative high-pressure alkaline electrolysis technology for hydrogen production.

This report is based on a PEACE project deliverable of the same name which was issued in November 2024 (M18 of project implementation) and produced by the WP6 leader (GG). It was a follow-up deliverable which elaborated upon the original PEACE Data Management Plan submitted in August 2023.

The PEACE Data management Plan is guided by the EU Open Science policy. Firstly, it aims to identify the main datasets and other research outputs that are to be produced within the project. Secondly, it ensures that the project's data management follows the FAIR principles of data policy. Thirdly, it represents a living platform for the project, allowing for further data management updates and enhancements. The first DMP has been prepared by the partner GG based on an internal survey of partners during months (M) 1-2 of the project implementation. This DMP II report takes over the original DMP, updates it and completes it with information gained through an internal survey of PEACE Executive Board members in M17/M18.

The PEACE project is to produce seven datasets and thirteen other research outputs (mostly public deliverables). All research data and outputs will be managed responsibly in accordance with the FAIR principles. Findability will be ensured through the use of persistent identifiers, metadata frameworks, and keywords. All datasets and outputs will be stored in trusted repositories, and open access will be provided whenever possible. However, some datasets have been identified as sensitive, and open access is currently considered contrary to the beneficiary's legitimate interests (as commercial exploitation is foreseen).

PEACE datasets available through open access will be licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike (CC-BY-SA), and metadata will be licensed under Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0). PEACE is using [Zenodo repository](#) to make datasets/other research outputs publicly and permanently available.

Interoperability and re-use of PEACE data will be enhanced by using open data formats, keywords, metadata, or readme files. The preservation of PEACE datasets is guaranteed for at least 5 years after the end of the project.

The PEACE DMP will be continuously updated as needed, with a final version to be in M36 of the project implementation.

2. PEACE Project Summary

The PEACE project represents a challenging research and innovation action in the field of hydrogen production, using the alkaline electrolysis (AEL) technologies. AEL technologies are known for their low investment costs and excellent scalability. The PEACE project aims to further improve the levelized cost of hydrogen produced by AEL. Therefore, efforts are focused on enhancing efficiency, maximizing current densities, and enabling better integration with downstream processes. By carefully designing a high-pressure stack and system, the performance and overall efficiency of the AEL process will be significantly improved, eliminating the need for additional compression for downstream processes. This, in turn, reduces the capital and operational expenses associated with hydrogen compressors, which are a substantial part of electrolysis systems' cost.

Within the PEACE project, a demonstrator of an AEL system exceeding 50 kW, capable of operating at pressures of up to 90 bars, will be designed and developed. This is achieved through a novel concept involving two-stage pressurization: by applying up to 60 bar hydraulic pressure using a pressure vessel in which a stack operates at additional 30 bar, resulting in up to 90 bar gas pressure. The integration of advanced components, innovative design, and optimized operation strategies will be explored through modelling and experimental testing, ultimately aiming to demonstrate a system with impressive efficiency characteristics: 70% lower heating value at a current density of 1 A/cm². The successful implementation of this technology promises a significant reduction in the cost of green hydrogen production.

The PEACE project scientific objectives are reinforced by a strong focus on sustainability and circularity aspects, as well as dedicated outreach activities. The PEACE project contributors comprise two SMEs, four research and development centres with established expertise in alkaline stack, system, and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), and one of the largest hydrogen production and utilization companies globally. This collaboration ensures a comprehensive approach to achieving the project's goals.

Finally, the project aims to propose use cases and the concept of an integrated plant. By combining all these developments, the goal is to achieve a technological breakthrough with a clear commercial perspective, positioning Europe as a leader in highly pressurized AEL technology within the next couple of years.

3. PEACE Data Summary

3.1. DMP principles

PEACE is a research and innovation action project funded by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership under Horizon Europe programme. Over the course of its 36-month implementation, several digital research datasets from different project team members will be generated. The formulation of a viable data management plan to guide the project team through the processes of data storage, availability, accessibility, and re-use is essential. Furthermore, the guiding principles of the EU Open Science policy (broadly outlined in Annex V of the EU grants Annotated Grant Agreement) provide a pathway for creating a comprehensive yet user-friendly plan to effectively manage data within the PEACE project. The PEACE project aims to:

- Deliver and use a comprehensive **DMP**, with regular updates scheduled for M18 and M36
- Handle its data in line with the **FAIR**¹ principles;
- Deposit its data, as soon as possible and at the latest by the end of the project, **in a trusted repository**
- **Ensure open access** to the research data via the repository under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0), provided this openness does not harm **beneficiary's legitimate interests or contradict any other constraints** (in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary's obligations under the GA, notably Article 13.1);
- Provide information via the repository about **any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data**
- Have its **metadata** open under (CC 0), providing basic information about the dataset origin and including links for related publications and other research outputs

3.2. DMP objectives

The current report represents an updated version of the original PEACE DMP. It takes over the original DMP and evolves relevant parts. This plan aids the project team in achieving efficient implementation of research objectives and additionally, facilitates effective communication and dissemination of project results.

The current PEACE DMP is produced within the Work package (WP) 1, Task 1.5. Its chief objectives are to:

- Identify main research digital datasets that will be produced
- Ensure data management in line with FAIR principles

¹ FAIR data policy principles are defined as: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

- Provide a living platform for data management updates and enhancements

The PEACE DMP covers digital research data generated within the project as well as other research outputs (namely public deliverables). It is based on dataset information that was collected through an internal survey of PEACE members within M1-M2 of the project. In M17/M18, another round of DMP screening took place to gather major updates in the field (see section 3.4). This document will be further updated and expanded as necessary in M36.

3.3. Data management in the PEACE project

Data management represents one of the tasks of the WP1, overseen by the project member GG. GG prepares the DMP in close cooperation and discussion with all project team members, aiming to achieve the established DMP objectives. Additionally, GG guides all the project team through the data life cycle process and informs them about their relevant data management obligations. GG is responsible for periodical reviews of the DMP, in collaboration with all project team members.

The PEACE Executive Board (EB) members, representing each project beneficiary, are responsible for addressing data management issues. The EB members serve as the primary points of contact for GG regarding data-related matters. The responsibility for dataset description, data collection, storage, deposition and archiving procedures, as well as for ensuring data handling compatibility with EC obligations, lies with the dataset owners, represented by the EB members.

3.4. Summary of PEACE data and other research outputs

PEACE project is structured to six work packages – four are dedicated to research and innovation in the field of hydrogen production with AEL technology. The remaining WP1 focuses on project management and WP6 on communication, dissemination and exploitation issues. The PEACE project has identified seven broad datasets that will be used in the PEACE project. Their brief description can be found in Table 1. Moreover, about thirteen other research outputs will be produced (see Table 2 and Table 3) – mostly deliverables that are destined for public use².

² Deliverables which dissemination level is "sensitive" will not be part of this DMP. First, they are not meant for public use and second, they are based on datasets described in Table 1.

3.4.1. Datasets

Dataset No.	Dat_1	Dat_2	Dat_3	Dat_4	Dat_5	Dat_6	Dat_7
Name	Cell component qualification	Operation strategies and simulation	Cell components qualification	Dual-stage high-pressure alkaline electrolyser operation	Integration concept of HP-AEL in a chemical plant	Conventional H2 production via AEL	PEACE H2 production
Owner	DLR	DLR	TU/e	BTU	HYCC BV	DTU	DTU
WP/task	2/2.1	5/5.1-5.5	2/2.1-2.3	4/4.1-4.7	5/5.6	6/6.1	6/6.1
Description	Electrochemical testing of cells or short stack	TEMPEST simulation data on the stack behaviour in a system in transient conditions.	Qualification of cell components	Experimental data from the demonstrator in operation	Process design data including sketches, mass & energy balances, cost estimates	The life cycle inventory of materials and energy necessary to produce H2 conventionally via electrolysis (benchmark for the PEACE data)	The life cycle inventory of materials and energy necessary to produce hydrogen via PEACE AEL
Type of data	Numeric, text, images	Numeric, text, images	Numeric	Numeric, text, images	Numeric, images, dtbs, models	Dtbs, models	Dtbs, models
Data format	Doc/docx, pdf, xls/xlsx, txt, jpg, tiff, png	Doc/docx, pdf, xls/xlsx, txt, jpg, tiff, png, mat-file	Xls/xlsx, sql, ids/idf	Xls/xlsx, pdf, csv, txt, jpg, png	Doc/docx, pdf, xls/xlsx, jpg, tiff	Xls/xlsx, pdf, txt	Xls/xlsx, pdf, txt
Repository	Zenodo	Zenodo	4TU.Research data	Open Energy Platform	Zenodo	supplement material of an OA article + DTU repository	supplement material of an OA article + DTU repository
Open access	Yes	Partly	Yes	Yes	Partly	Yes	Yes
Reasons for closed data	Commercial exploitation	Commercial exploitation	x	x	Commercial exploitation + sensitive info on beneficiary	x	x
Metadata	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table 1 PEACE Datasets

PEACE datasets consist mainly of project-generated numerical data produced through direct measurements and simulations, except for the Life Cycle Inventory dataset (**Dat_6**). This benchmark dataset for the purpose of LCA of the PEACE high-pressure AEL will be based on re-used data collected from literature, surveys, or simulations. For LCA purposes, this dataset will be analysed jointly with dataset **Dat_7**, which covers similar characteristics generated from PEACE experiments and simulations. These datasets could prove valuable to LCA practitioners in fields such as renewable energy, energy production, hydrogen production, or power-to-X technologies.

Direct measurement data represent the core of the dataset **Dat_1** and **Dat_3**, both at the level of the electrolytical cell or short stack, and **Dat_4** at the PEACE demonstrator stack level. Datasets **Dat_1** and **Dat_3** will aid identifying optimal cell and stack components to achieve the defined system efficiency targets. They can be further used by researchers validating models and businesses involved in electrolysis hydrogen production. BTU data (**Dat_4**) constitutes outcome experimental data from the PEACE high-pressure AEL demonstrator, confirming its performance and efficiency. These data might further serve electrolysis companies, research entities, or production safety organisations.

Conversely, simulation data (**Dat_2**), collected by the coordinating institution DLR, will analyse the behaviour of the PEACE high-pressure AEL behaviour under transient conditions to formulate optimized operating strategies. These data might be a valuable resource for industries involved in electrolyser production, particularly water electrolysis and renewable energy, as well as for academics.

Lastly, HYCC will contribute with its dataset **Dat_5**, focusing on the integration of the PEACE high-pressure electrolyser within a chemical plant involving at least two downstream processes. This dataset encompasses numerical data, images, databases, and models. The design models will include heat integration, energy and mass balances, cost estimates, all with the aim to assessing and enhancing the impact of PEACE technologies. These data could prove highly valuable to companies and stakeholders interested in hydrogen production and/or use, as well as to researchers developing technologies who seek to assess impacts or establish design targets.

Most datasets are expected to have a **size** equal to or less than 5 GB. Simulation data (**Dat_2**) could be larger in size (in the tens of GBs), but a selection process will be employed to maintain a manageable size, keeping within the Zenodo repository's 50GB limit.

3.4.2. Other research outputs

	Oro_1	Oro_2	Oro_3	Oro_4	Oro_5	Oro_6	Oro_7
Name	Stack project specifications	Stack project calculation	Stack/cell operative drawings	PEACE DMP	D3.1 Stack components	D4.3 HAZOP/FMEA	D5.2 Optimized operation strategy
Owner	MMI	MMI	MMI	GG	MMI	MMI	DLR
WP/task	3/3.1-3.4	3/3.1-3.4	3/3.1-3.4	1/1.5	3/3.1-3.4	4/4.3	5/5.1-5.6
Description	List of the test items to be produced, with features, materials and construction materials	Calculation, description and excel files of the sizing of different items	Mechanical drawings of different produced items	Public version of the project DMP	Public deliverable on stack components (1 cell, end plates) qualified for pressure standing, mounting and initial testing	Public deliverable on HAZOP and FMEA analysis results and safety protocol	Public deliverable on optimized operation strategy for high pressure alkaline water electrolyser
Type of data	Text, images	Numeric, text, images, mechanical design	Numeric, text, images, mechanical design	Text	Numeric, images, dtbs, models	Numeric, text, images	Numeric, text, images
Data format	Xls/xlsx, doc/docx, pdf	Doc/docx, pdf, xls/xlsx	Doc/docx, pdf, 4D model	Pdf	Pdf, xls/xlsx, jpg, tiff	Pdf, xls/xlsx, jpg, tiff,	Pdf, xls/xlsx, jpg, tiff, png
Repository	Zenodo	Zenodo	Zenodo	Zenodo	Zenodo	Zenodo	Zenodo
Open access	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Reasons for closed data	x	x	Commercial exploitation	x	x	x	x
Metadata	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table 2 PEACE Other research outputs - part A

	Oro_8	Oro_9	Oro_10	Oro_11	Oro_12	Oro_13
Name	D6.2 Project website and PR	D6.3 Public workshop	D6.8 LCA	PEDR (public version)	D6.9 Update I of PEDR	D6.10 Update II of PEDR
Owner	GG	DLR	DTU	GG	GG	GG
WP/task	6/6.2	6/6.3	6/6.1	6/6.4	6/6.4	6/6.4
Description	Public deliverable on operational project website; communication and PR kit	Public deliverable on project workshop (report/ presentations)	Public deliverable on the Life Cycle Analysis of the PEACE AEL	Public version of the project deliverable on the Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR)	Public deliverable on the first update of the PEDR	Public deliverable on the second update of the PEDR
Type of data	Text, images	Numeric, text, images	Numeric, text, images	Text, images	Text, images	Text, images
Data format	Pdf, jpg	Pdf, jpg	Pdf, jpg	Pdf, jpg	Pdf, jpg	Pdf, jpg
Repository	Zenodo	Zenodo	Zenodo	Zenodo	Zenodo	Zenodo
Open access	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Reasons for closed data	x	x	x	x	x	x
Metadata	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table 3 PEACE Other research outputs - part B

PEACE team members anticipate to produce about thirteen so called other research outputs. MMI will generate three outputs (**Oro_1, Oro_2 and Oro_3**) related to the AEL stack, including stack specifications, calculations, and drawings. These outputs will be manufactured as part of the project and will be founded on datasets from other project members. These outputs are potentially useful for other electrolyser stack producers.

Among the thirty-one PEACE deliverables, eight have been assigned “public” dissemination level and will be covered within the PEACE data management plan. **Oro_5, Oro_6, and Oro_7**, along with **Oro_9** (which would summarise the achieved project results), represent scientific outputs that could prove valuable to researchers and businesses engaged in the hydrogen production. Deliverable **Oro_10** aims to engage practitioners in matters of circularity and sustainability.

Conversely, **Oro_8, Oro_11, Oro_12 and Oro_13** represent communication and dissemination reports dedicated not only for the scientific community, but also for the general public. Oro_8, Oro_11 and Oro_12 have been already deposited at [ZENODO PEACE Community page](#), along with a public version of PEACE DMP(**Oro_4**).

4. PEACE FAIR data (Findable-Accessible-Interoperable-Reuseable)

The PEACE project is built on open and collaborative work, and planned sharing of knowledge, whilst adhering to the data policy principle of achieving maximum openness as early and widely as possible. All research data generated by the PEACE project will be managed responsibly in accordance with the FAIR principles and Horizon Europe obligations (as described in the guidelines of the Annotated Grant Agreement - Article 17).

To ensure **findability** of PEACE data, all datasets (including other research outputs) will be assigned persistent identifier, preferably DOIs, through carefully selected trusted repositories. Metadata frameworks will accompany all datasets and will be openly accessible under the public domain dedication CC0. Metadata will provide information about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); Horizon Europe funding, grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata will include persistent identifiers for linked publications and other research outputs. Metadata will be stored within the repositories in JSON format and will be harvestable.

Simultaneously, PEACE datasets will employ common keywords such as hydrogen, alkaline electrolyser, and pressurization.

The **storage** of PEACE data will not be centralised, instead, the project will maintain the well-established storage practices of individual project team members. Some project team members will use their respective institutional repositories, others will opt for general or domain-specific repositories (see further) For internal sharing of data, other research outputs, or documents among the PEACE team members, a project internal site (within the secure coordinator's server) is used.

In line with the FAIR principles, PEACE datasets and other research outputs are intended to be deposited into **trusted repositories** as soon as possible and, at the latest, by the end of the project. If the given dataset underpins a scientific publication, it will be deposited no later than the time of publication. Most datasets and all other research outputs will use [Zenodo](#) repository, a trusted open-source repository with metadata openly available under CC0 licence, as mandated by Horizon Europe. Datasets on Zenodo will receive DOIs and can be linked to related publications or datasets. Availability of the data is planned at least for 10 years, but it will presumably align with the general conditions of the repository. PEACE team members will not be obliged to include the information on software needed to read the data – this will remain an option only, though already agreed upon by some. Moreover, project's [PEACE Zenodo community](#) was established in M10 (March 2024), which might serve as a long-term and widely accessible platform for PEACE publications, datasets and other research outputs. PEACE team members are encouraged to use this platform for their dataset storage. Currently, Oro_4, Oro_8, Oro_11 and Oro_12 have been deposited there.

University PEACE project members, DTU and TU/e, will follow their usual practices and deposit their dataset (Dat_3, Dat_6, and Dat_7) within their respective trusted institutional repositories. DTU will use its university repository [ScienceRepository](#) – which grants DOIs to all datasets and offers unlimited data storage. TU/e's repository, [4TU.Researchdata](#), is dedicated to science, engineering and design, offering up to 100GB of free data upload per

year, with granted DOIs and openly published metadata, as required by Horizon Europe. BTU Dat_4 will be deposited in a domain-specific repository, the [Open Energy Platform](#), an open infrastructure for energy system research. Datasets are identifiable (by id), openly accessible with rich metadata published.

An overview of PEACE data **accessibility** is presented in Table 1 - 3. The PEACE project fully acknowledges Open Science and Open Access guidelines, thus ensuring that all PEACE data will be managed in line with the principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. For most datasets, open access will be granted at the time of datasets publication. However, open access to Dat_2, Dat_5, and Oro_3 is currently perceived as against the beneficiary’s legitimate interests (due to anticipated commercial exploitation). These sensitive datasets (as specified in Art. 13.1 of the PEACE Grant Agreement) are deemed commercially valuable, and their immediate openness would undermine their exploitation potential. As a result, they will remain closed (or under embargoed access) for the duration specified in the Data Sheet of the Grant Agreement (i.e., 5 years after the final payment). Nonetheless, PEACE beneficiaries support the EC Open Science policy and have outlined a potential division of these datasets. Part of these datasets will remain closed for the reasons mentioned, while the other part might be accessible openly. However, the decision to keep certain PEACE data closed is subject to periodic review and may change.

The **interoperability** of PEACE data will be enhanced by employing open data formats (such as doc, pdf, xls, csv, jpg), or standard language keywords. As the FAIR data policy aims to optimise **the re-use of data**, the PEACE project members will use well-described (meta)data to ensure the replicability of datasets across different contexts. For non-self-explanatory data, various strategies will be implemented to facilitate data validation and re-use. DTU will provide open comprehensive descriptions in the methodology section of the linked peer-reviewed articles that will be using Dat_6 and Dat_7. The cell components data of TU/e (Dat_3) will include additional relevant information, such as experimental conditions (temperature, pressure, concentration, type of electrode, reference electrode, type of potentiostat, etc.). Similarly, for the considered open parts of the Dat_5, a readme file will be generated, containing all necessary information for interpretation and reproduction (reference conditions, modelling assumptions, settings, etc.).

Lastly, PEACE datasets in open access will be **licensed** under the latest available version of a Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike (CC-BY-SA), requiring attribution of authorship. Metadata will be licensed under Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0).

The **costs** associated with supporting the FAIR principles in PEACE will primarily involve datasets that directly underpin peer-reviewed articles (such as Dat_6, Dat_7), for which publication fees for open access are borne by the authors. Otherwise, the repositories that have been chosen by the PEACE project team members offer free data storage services. As personnel costs are assumed, a specific data steward position has not been established. However, data management falls within the responsibilities of GG, with approximately 0,75 PM dedicated to fulfilling this task. At the project level, data management is the responsibility of each Executive Board member, and the related workload has not been calculated separately.

The **long-term preservation** of PEACE datasets is guaranteed for at least 5 years after the end of the project, in line with the general conditions of the chosen repositories, which typically offer data retention for more than 10 years.

Regarding **ethical or legal issues** affecting data sharing, it is important to note that no PEACE research datasets or other research outputs involve personal data. However, some project team members express concerns about the potential conflict between open data sharing and their intellectual property rights. Therefore, certain datasets might not be fully accessible, as indicated in Table 1.

Another potential source of data sensitivity has been introduced by BTU, as certain PEACE datasets might have a relevance to the EU Regulation 2021/821 on dual-use export controls. The dataset owners are to assess this issue in line with their internal regulations and practices.

Lastly, as a part of PEACE data management, we need to consider **other data handling procedures** stemming from the institutional practices of some PEACE scientific team members. These practices encompass the internal procedures of DLR, DTU, and BTU. Nevertheless, no explicit conflicts are anticipated, as all of these PEACE project contributors are aligned with the open access policy³. Each entity is responsible for complying with its own institutional data regulations, and in case of a potential conflict with the PEACE DMP, GG is to be informed and a conflict resolution procedure will be initiated.

³ Broschüre (2018); DTU Library; University Library Cottbus-Senftenberg.

5. Conclusion

The PEACE Data Management Plan represents a living document that will guide the project team members through the entire data lifecycle while adhering to the principles of the EU Open Science policy, including the FAIR principles of data management. The current DMP report is a public update of the former deliverable of M3. It takes over the original DMP and upgrades relevant parts. Updates on datasets are based on an internal survey of the PEACE EB members during M17/M18 and are summarised in the tables of the section 3.4.

PEACE DMP II covers seven digital research data generated within the project, along with thirteen other research outputs (namely public deliverables). All datasets and outputs will be managed in accordance with the FAIR data principles, ensuring their findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. This approach aims to contribute to the successful achievement of the PEACE project goals and to boost the project impact, thereby enriching the European realm of science and innovation.

6. References

4TU.Researchdata - <https://data.4tu.nl>

Broschüre: Grundlagen zum Forschungsdatenmanagement im DLR (2018), <https://www.dlr.de/de/medien/publikationen/broschueren/grundlagen-zum-forschungsdatenmanagement-im-dlr>

DTU Library – Open Access - <https://www.bibliotek.dtu.dk/en/publishing/open-access>,

EU Grants AGA - Annotated Grant Agreement, EU Funding Programmes 2021-2027, version 1.0, draft, April 2023 - https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

Grant Agreement, Project 101101343 – PEACE – HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2022-1

Open Energy Platform - <https://openenergy-platform.org/>

Regulation (EU) 2021/821 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 setting up a Union regime for the control of exports, brokering, technical assistance, transit and transfer of dual-use items

ScienceRepository - <https://sciencerepository.dk/>

University Library Cottbus-Senftenberg – Open Access - <https://www.b-tu.de/en/bibliothek/publishing/open-access#c136861>

ZENODO - <https://zenodo.org/>